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Technical Report

Unmasking bias in large language
models: A survey

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Abstract

The rapid adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) across various industries has raised significant concerns about potential risks, particularly biases in large language models (LLMs). These models are widely used in applications from customer service and healthcare to educational tools, influencing decisions that impact diverse populations. However, LLMs often inherit and amplify biases present in the large datasets on which they are trained, risking the reinforcement of stereotypes and marginalisation of certain groups. This work presents a comprehensive survey on bias and fairness in LLMs. It explores various sources of biases, and the harms (e.g., toxicity, discrimination, etc.) they can cause. To address these challenges, bias detection, mitigation, and evaluation approaches are reviewed. The study concludes by outlining limitations and offering insights into future research directions for formulating effective strategies. The findings emphasise the significant need for ongoing research and proactive regulatory measures to address and mitigate bias in LLMs to ensure that AI technologies are deployed ethically, equitably, and with public trust as a priority.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made substantial strides in recent years, with large language models (LLMs) which aim to estimate the likelihood of a given sequence of words appearing in a sentence through various statistical and probabilistic methods. The most prominent ones are OpenAI's GPT-4 [1], Meta's LLaMa [2], Google's Gemini [3], and Anthropic's Claude [4]. This groundbreaking revolution has significantly enhanced natural language processing. As a result, language models have proved their use in a variety of applications, such as chatbots, automated translation, question answering, customer experience, and assisting in a multitude of tasks. However, like any tool, they are not without flaws and bring serious risks. One major risk is bias. Addressing bias through normative frameworks is crucial, as emphasised by the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI [5]. It states that AI actors must strive to minimise and avoid reinforcing biases to ensure fairness. To date, however, AI systems often amplify existing human, structural, and social biases, which can cause individual and societal harm. But what exactly is bias in LLMs?

Bias, as defined by Kahneman [6], is "the tendency to make systematic errors in judgement or decisions based on factors that are irrelevant or immaterial to the task at hand." In language models, bias appears as outputs reflecting prejudiced, unfair, or unbalanced views, often learned from biased datasets on the internet, including books, articles, social media posts, and more. Unfortunately, the internet is riddled with biases of all kinds-cultural, gender, racial, ethnic, and political are among others. To illustrate, if an LLM is trained on texts that predominantly portray women in traditional roles, it might generate content that reinforces these stereotypes (i.e., over-generalised belief about a particular group of people). Similarly, if the data includes more male-authored texts, the model might produce outputs that align more with male viewpoints [7]. When LLMs are trained on data containing such biases, they inadvertently learn to replicate these harmful patterns in their outputs. This not only perpetuates existing social biases that can also exacerbate them, leading to the marginalisation and discrimination of vulnerable groups.

Biased models impact fairness, ethics, and trust in AI, risking reinforcement of stereotypes, affecting decision-making processes, influencing societal norms and behaviours, and impacting the model's reliability and fairness [8]. For example, OpenAI's ChatGPT contains biases, with a tendency

toward Western perspectives due to its predominantly Western training data and also performs best in English language tasks. Its conversational nature can also reinforce user biases, particularly in educational settings, highlighting the need for critical evaluation of AI-generated content [9]. A recent study [5] also examined biases in three major LLMs: OpenAI’s GPT-2 and ChatGPT, and Meta’s Llama 2. The study highlighted how these models used in decision-making and as conversational agents, exhibit biases through gendered word associations and content generation. For example, Llama 2 generated sexist and misogynistic content in 20% of instances and homophobic content 70% of the time. Thus, understanding the pervasive impact of biases in language models and how to mitigate them is essential to building fair and reliable AI systems and tools.

Fig. 1: Overview of bias research: Insights on bias and strategies for bias detection, debiasing and evaluation

This work presents a survey to unmask bias in LLMs, with an overview depicted in Figure 1. The key contributions of this study are as follows: **(i)** providing a comprehensive categorisation and analysis of various sources and types of bias. This foundational understanding is important for identifying where and how biases emerge in LLMs; **(ii)** delving into methodologies for measuring these biases, detailing approaches used to identify and quantify biases and clarifies the landscape of bias detection in LLMs; **(iii)** reviewing a range of bias mitigation strategies tailored to different phases of LLM development lifecycle. This includes approaches for mitigating bias during the pre-processing, training, and post-processing phases and various bias evaluation approaches, benchmark datasets, and tools, providing an overview of the current resources available for bias assessment and mitigation in LLMs; and **(iv)** identifying gaps in the existing literature and providing a roadmap for future work. This includes the need for more sophisticated and nuanced bias detection methods, the development of more effective and scalable debiasing techniques, and the creation of comprehensive evaluation frameworks that can accurately assess the impact of biases and the effectiveness of debiasing strategies. By highlighting these open problems, this paper aims to guide future research efforts towards addressing the critical challenges in creating more fair and equitable LLM technologies.

In the remainder of the work, the sources of bias in LLMs (Section 2), and the resulting bias-related harms (Section 3) are analysed. Subsequently, bias detection (Section 4) and debiasing (Section 5) approaches are reviewed. Then, resources for bias evaluation are presented (Section 6). Finally, limitations of existing works (Section 7) and directions for future research are discussed (Section 8).

2 Sources of Bias

Bias in AI and LLMs can emerge at any stage of their development from the initial design, and modelling decisions to data collection, processing and deployment [10]. These biases generally fall into four categories:

Bias in Data. The training datasets for LLMs often do not represent the full diversity of the population, resulting in poor performance for certain social groups. Essential contexts might be missing, and the proxies used as labels may inaccurately capture the intended outcomes. Furthermore, data aggregation can hide distinct social groups, making the model overly generalised or biased toward the majority group. Even when the data is properly collected, it still carries inherent historical and structural biases.

The data generation phase begins with data collection. This involves defining a target population, sampling from it, and identifying and measuring features and labels. The dataset is then split into training and test sets, and benchmark datasets are also collected, often using a different process. During model training, the model is optimised on the training data, and the test and benchmark data are used to evaluate it. Once finalised, the model is integrated into a real-world context. This is a cyclic process, where decisions made by the model influence the world and affect future data collection and decisions. At the data generation phase, we encounter historical bias, representation bias, measurement bias, and training data bias.

Historical bias is where past societal patterns are encoded into the data. For example, word embeddings may associate certain professions with gender due to historical gender roles. Word embeddings are an increasingly popular application of neural networks wherein enormous text corpora are taken as input and words therein are mapped to a vector in some high dimensional space. Two commonly used approaches are word2vec [11] and GloVe [12]. In word embeddings, words are represented in a continuous vector space where semantically similar words are mapped to nearby points [13], or to predict the likelihood of seeing words in the context of another such as synonym similarity, linear word relationships, and analogies e.g., man : woman :: king : queen. Their use is now standard in training complex language models. However, it has been observed that word embeddings are prone to expressing the bias inherent in the data it is extracted from and to encoding systematic biases such as against women and ethnic minorities, implicating many NLP systems in scaling up social injustice [14, 15, 16]. These biases are subsequently passed on to downstream tasks such as co-reference resolution [17, 18] or question answering [19]. Current state-of-art co-reference systems mainly build on word embeddings and risk inheriting their bias. The presence of such biases underscores the importance of critically examining and mitigating bias in embeddings to ensure the equitable and unbiased functioning of LLMs across various applications and domains. We also face *representation bias*, where certain groups are either overrepresented or underrepresented in the training data. Additionally, there is *measurement bias*, which occurs when data is collected using proxies like zip codes that unintentionally introduce bias.

The training data for LLMs typically includes a wide variety of sources like books, websites, and other text. This data often contains societal biases and stereotypes, whether intentional or not. These biases can be based on age, gender, race, ethnicity, religion, and more. When an LLM learns from biased data, it can inadvertently learn these biases as well. For instance, the model might associate certain professions more with one gender than another, or it might generate text that reinforces stereotypes about a particular race or ethnicity [20]. *Training data bias* in LLMs encompasses sociodemographic, sentiment and human annotation biases inherit in training data.

Sociodemographic bias refers to biases related to social and demographic groups [21]. Such biases often stem from imbalanced or skewed representations in the training data, leading to LLMs

perpetuating stereotypes or underrepresenting certain groups. Sociodemographic bias is particularly concerning as it can lead to differential model performances across various social groups [22], and language models can amplify biases by associating certain lexical items more strongly with particular social groups and may reinforce gender, racial or ethnic prejudices [7, 23, 24, 25]. There are several types of sociodemographic biases in language models including:

- racial bias [23, 24], when models are biased against certain races.
- gender bias [7, 25], when models are biased against a particular gender.
- ethnic bias [26] when models are partial towards certain ethnicity.
- age bias, sexual orientation bias [27], and nationality bias [28].
- downstream bias [29], e.g., biographies with she/her pronouns are less frequently classified as belonging to certain traditionally male-dominated professions—such as “surgeon”—which could result in lower recruitment or call-back rates for job candidates if the classifier is used by an employer.
- other biases are underrepresentation of certain groups or perspectives, ableism, disability, religion, political views, physical appearance, and socioeconomic status biases [21, 30].

Bias in the sentiment (positive, negative, neutral) of text generated by LLMs, called *sentiment bias*, occurs when the emotion of generated texts is influenced by attributes of the prompt and/or by social biases embedded in the training data, is also a significant concern in the literature [8, 31]. Sentiment bias has tendency of LLMs to associate positive or negative sentiment with particular demographic or social categories in an unbalanced way. For example, an LLM might consistently generate more positive reviews or comments for products when described with language typically associated with a specific gender or ethnicity. Addressing sentiment bias is crucial because this may lead to discrimination. As an example of sentiment bias, GPT-2 was found to produce more positive emotion in relation to the profession of “baker” than for “accountant” [8].

Annotation bias, particularly significant in the context of training data for LLMs, can be profoundly influential, especially in tasks like coreference resolution, which is a task aimed at identifying phrases or mentions when different words refer to the same entity in a text [18]. This bias emerges when the human-annotated datasets, used for training models, carry the annotators’ subjective interpretations and perspectives. For example, annotators may bring their own assumptions or cultural contexts into the annotation process, affecting how they interpret pronouns, named entities, and relationships within a text.

Bias in Model Selection. The training and inference processes of a model can increase bias beyond what is in the training data. The choice of optimisation function, the treatment of training instances or social groups, and the ranking of outputs during training or inference can all influence a model’s biases.

In the model training phase, we encounter various types of bias such as learning bias, aggregation bias, and evaluation bias. *Learning bias* can emerge when the model overfits to patterns in the data, amplifying those biases. An AI system that discards data based on certain notions of completeness or validity may unfairly favour specific inputs from the onset. For example, a system may prefer male resumes over female resumes when hiring. *Aggregation bias* happens when data from different groups is averaged without considering key differences, leading to biased outputs. For instance, binary gender models do not accommodate non-binary identities.

Bias in Evaluation. Benchmark datasets used for evaluation may not represent the entire population, leading to optimisation that favours those included in the benchmark. The chosen metric can affect the perceived properties of the model, potentially hiding performance disparities between social groups or influencing the focus on certain types of errors. Thus, *evaluation bias* emerges when the evaluation or test data used to assess the model does not represent the diversity of real-world applications, leading to skewed evaluations.

Bias in Deployment. An LLM might be used in settings different from its original purpose, such as with or without human intermediaries in automated decisions. The user interface can also alter how users perceive the model’s behaviour. Additionally, adjusting models based on user feedback without considering the demographic diversity of users which can introduce new biases and lead to inappropriate outcomes. At the deployment stage, we encounter deployment bias, user-AI assistant interaction bias, and unintended bias.

Deployment bias, where the model performs poorly in contexts it wasn’t trained for. For example, language models trained on internet text might make improper associations between psychiatric terms and specific ethnic or gender groups.

User-AI assistant interaction bias in LLMs, is a nuanced form of bias that emerges through the model’s dynamic engagement with users. This bias occurs when an AI assistant, learning from user inputs over time, begins to reflect the patterns, preferences, or prejudices present in those inputs. For example, if users frequently interact with the AI assistant using a certain style of speech or expressing particular viewpoints, the model may increasingly generate responses that align with these styles and viewpoints. This can lead to a feedback loop where the AI assistant unintentionally enhances or propagates certain biases. This phenomenon is particularly evident in cases where user interactions include biased or unbalanced perspectives, which the AI, without proper guardrails, might learn and perpetuate. Such biases are not intrinsic to the AI’s initial training data but develop over time through its interactions, making them challenging to predict and mitigate. Addressing interaction bias requires ongoing monitoring and recalibration of models, as well as the incorporation of diverse user interactions to avoid the reinforcement of narrow or harmful perspectives [30].

Human feedback is commonly utilised to finetune AI assistants. A particularly popular technique for leveraging human feedback is reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) [32]. However, human labels are often imperfect, and human approval can sometimes be obtained through undesirable means. This phenomenon is defined as “sycophancy” [33, 34]. Sycophancy is a general behaviour of state-of-the-art AI assistants, likely driven in part by human preference judgments favouring sycophantic responses [33].

Unintended bias refers to biases that emerge unpredictably and are not directly tied to the training data or specific tasks [20]. These biases often surface through novel combinations of inputs or unique user interactions, revealing unforeseen implications of the model’s learned associations. The model is not intended to discriminate between the gender of the people expressed in a comment so if the model does so, this is called unintended bias [35]. This contrast with fairness, which focuses on the potential negative impact on society (e.g., harmful stereotypes) and the unequal treatment of individuals [32, 36]. Since the presence of unintended bias can affect fairness in various ways, its definition and mitigation are crucial to improving fairness across a wide range of use cases. Addressing unintended biases requires continuous monitoring and updating of models in real-world settings, alongside the development of robust testing procedures that can simulate a wide range of user interactions and contexts.

3 Bias Related Harms in LLMs

Biases in LLMs extend beyond the system, adversely affecting individuals and groups [37]. These harms include:

Stereotyping. Stereotypes are broad, generalised beliefs about individuals based on their group identity. They persist in human thought by disregarding evidence that contradicts them. In the context of AI, stereotypes can be unintentionally embedded in models, leading to biased outputs that reflect or sustain societal prejudices [38, 39, 40].

Disparagement. Disparagement refers to behaviours by a model that suggest some groups are less valuable or deserving of respect and resources than others [41, 42].

Erasure. Erasure is the under-representation or absence of certain social groups in data, whether intentional or not. It occurs when there is a mismatch between reality and the data selected to represent it and can inadvertently reinforce existing power dynamics through methods like improper averaging. While models may quantitatively reflect group sizes, the challenge lies in ensuring the size does not disproportionately influence prominence in the output, thus addressing the potential effects of these representations [43].

Toxicity. Toxic language in LLMs is a significant issue that arises predominantly due to biases inherent in their training data [24]. The presence of toxic language in training datasets can often reflect and amplify societal prejudices and stereotypes, particularly targeting specific demographic groups. This type of language, characterised by derogatory, offensive, or harmful expressions, disproportionately impacts groups based on race, gender, ethnicity, sexuality, or other identity markers [35].

Discrimination. This harm occurs when language models produce biased or prejudiced content against certain groups based on race, gender, ethnicity, or other characteristics, whether in hiring decisions or in access to healthcare. This can perpetuate stereotypes, reinforce societal biases, and contribute to unequal treatment, negatively impacting affected groups and undermining efforts toward fairness and equality [44].

Misinformation and disinformation. These forms can be generated, spreading misleading information or biased views (e.g., in medicine, law, etc.), leading to further harm such as influencing public perception and decision-making [45, 46].

Trust. Repeated exposure to biased outputs can undermine trust in AI systems, particularly in contexts when human-computer interaction is essential. If users perceive that the AI is consistently biased or harmful, they may lose confidence in its ability to be fair and objective. Potential harms include unsafe use due to users misjudging or mistakenly trusting the model, psychological vulnerabilities and privacy violations of the user, and social harm from perpetuating discriminatory associations via product design (e.g., making “assistant” tools by default “female”) [46].

4 Bias Detection

Bias detection involves quantifying the level or extent of bias present in a system, model, or dataset. Bias measure can be defined as an evaluation standard that includes a metric(s) applied to a dataset or used to assess behaviour in language models. So, it is about identifying and understanding the nature of the bias whether it is related to gender, race, or another factor. It is a challenging process because it is often hidden within complex LLMs. This section addresses relevant metrics to assess the

bias exhibited in a dataset or in a model's behaviour.

4.1 Embedding-based Metrics

The biases in word embeddings can lead to biased outputs in various applications, like text generation, sentiment analysis, and more. This can foster stereotypes and discrimination, leading to ethical concerns and potential harm. Embedding-based methods measure bias in the word embeddings used by the language models. Word embeddings are vector representations of words that capture the semantic relationship between them. These methods detect bias by analysing how closely words representing certain social groups are associated with stereotypical or neutral terms in the embedding space.

Word Embedding Association Test (WEAT). WEAT is a statistical test that detects bias in word embeddings using cosine similarity and averaging methods, paired with hypothesis testing. To illustrate, two sets of target words (e.g., programmer, engineer) and two sets of attribute words (e.g., man, male, and woman, female) are considered. The null hypothesis is that there is no difference between the two sets of target words in terms of their relative similarity to the two sets of attribute words. The permutation test measures the (un)likelihood of the null hypothesis by computing the probability that a random permutation of the attribute words would produce the observed (or greater) difference in sample means. Then, bias is calculated as the differential association of target words with attribute sets based on cosine similarity. If male names are more closely associated with career-related words like "engineer" and female names with caregiving roles like "nurse" or with family terms like "mother", this indicates gender bias in the embeddings [14].

Sentence Encoder Association Test (SEAT). SEAT is the extension of WEAT, state-of-the-art sentence encoders which compares sets of sentences, rather than sets of words, by applying WEAT to the vector representation of a sentence to capture bias [16].

Mean Average Cosine Similarity (MAC). MAC extends the SEAT to a multi-class setting. It measures bias by calculating the average cosine similarity between target word embeddings (e.g., racial or gender groups) and sets of biased attribute words, providing a score that captures multi-class bias in embeddings [47].

Embedding Coherence Test (ECT). ECT measures the amount of explicit bias. It simplifies an attribute category, like female, into a single vector by averaging the embeddings of related attribute words such as she, women, and girl [38].

Contextualised Embedding Association Test (CEAT). CEAT is an extension of WEAT that can summarise the magnitude of overall bias in neural language models by incorporating a random-effects model. This method automatically detects the attributes that have high associations with the intersectional group from a set of word embeddings [48].

Projection on Gender Direction. Bolukbasi et al. [15] proposed a method to detect gender bias in word embeddings by analysing their alignment with a computed gender direction. This direction is derived from predefined gender word pairs (e.g., he-she or man-woman) using techniques like Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Words are then projected onto this direction, and the magnitude of the projection indicates the extent of their gender bias. A higher magnitude reflects stronger gendered associations, enabling the identification of unintended gender bias in embeddings.

Intersectional Bias Detection (IBD). This approach is designed to detect biases associated with intersectional group members, defined as individuals belonging to two or more social categories sim-

ultaneously. IBD identifies words linked to these intersectional groups by leveraging contextualised word embeddings to reveal the distribution of human-like biases in language models [48].

Bias Analogy Test (BAT). Lauscher et al. [49] assessed the number of biased analogies that can be retrieved from an embedding space based on the explicit bias specification. Then, the authors created two query vectors from each analogy and ranked the vectors in the vector space according to the Euclidean distance with each of the query vectors. In a biased space, the vector is expected to be ranked higher for the query than the vectors of terms from the opposing attribute set (e.g., for a gender-biased space woman is expected to be ranked higher than father or boy for the query man – programmer + homemaker).

Relational Inner Product Association (RIPA). Ethayarajh et al. [50] use the inner product instead of cosine similarity to account for vector magnitude and directionality in measuring bias. In this work, for any given word in the vocabulary, the authors compare its gender association in the training corpus to its gender association in the embedding space. Words are grouped into three categories with respect to gender: biased, appropriate, and neutral. A list of biased and appropriate words was created using Bolukbasi et al. [15]’s lists of gender-biased and gender-appropriate analogies.

inBias. Multilingual word embeddings represent words from different languages using the same embedding space which enables cross-lingual transfer learning. The model is trained on a labelled data-rich language and adopted to another language where no or a small portion of labelled data is available. There are several works that focus on getting the multilingual word embeddings. Zhao et al. [51] analysed the gender bias in multilingual (e.g., English, Spanish, German and French) word embeddings. This work introduced the *inBias* metric for quantifying intrinsic bias in multilingual word embeddings from word-level perspective. Then, they introduced the dataset collected for quantifying bias in different languages. The goal of this metric is aligned to that of WEAT [14]. It calculates the difference of targets (e.g., occupations) corresponding to different attributes (gender).

Sentence Bias Score. The Sentence Bias Score is a method to estimate gender bias in sentence embeddings. This metric leverages the semantic importance of words within a sentence to evaluate the extent of bias. By assessing how much individual words contribute to the overall meaning of a sentence, the bias score helps differentiate between neutral and biased gender information at the sentence level. This score can identify stereotyped sentences (i.e., ethnic, religious) that contribute to increasing gender bias in the embeddings encoded by the model [52].

4.2 Probabilistic Metrics

Probabilistic measures detect bias by assessing how likely a model is to generate stereotypical versus neutral completions.

Context Association Test (CAT). Nadeem et al. [23] introduced two different association tests, intrasentence and intersentence CATs, to measure language modelling and stereotypical bias at sentence level and discourse level. The intrasentence task measures the bias and the language modelling ability for sentence-level reasoning. CAT evaluates the probability of stereotypical, anti-stereotypical, or unrelated completions of the model. For example, in completing "Girls tend to be more _ than boys" options like "soft" (stereotypical), "determined" (anti-stereotypical) or "fish" (unrelated) are provided. The model’s bias is measured by which word it favours.

Stereotype Score (SS). Stereotype score [23] quantifies a model’s preference for stereotypical completions over anti-stereotypical ones within a given context. It is calculated by comparing the likelihood scores assigned by the model to stereotypical and anti-stereotypical options.

Language Model Score (LMS). This metric measures the percentage of examples for which a model prefers a meaningful association (either the stereotypical association or the anti-stereotypical association) as opposed to the unrelated association. This percentage is defined as the language modelling score of a model [23].

Log Probability Bias Score (LPBS). The log probability bias score [53] evaluates bias by calculating the difference in log probabilities assigned by a language model to sentences with biased versus unbiased contexts. Specifically, it measures how the model’s predictions change when swapping key terms (e.g., man vs woman) in otherwise identical sentences. A higher score indicates stronger bias in the model’s contextualised word representations.

Discovery of Correlations (DisCo). DisCo [25] is a method to quantify the likelihood of associations between specific concepts and gendered terms in language models. This metric employs sentence templates with placeholders, such as [PERSON] *studied* [BLANK] *at college*, where the [PERSON] is replaced with gendered terms (e.g., he, she, they) or gendered-specific nouns (e.g., poetess), and the model predicts likely completions for the [BLANK] slot. By analysing the probabilities assigned to various completions, this metric measures the strength of gendered associations in the model’s predictions. For instance, if the model consistently predicts nursing or literature for she and engineering or physics for he, it reveals stereotypical gender correlations. Lauscher et al. [49] refines this method by filtering predictions based on a threshold instead of focusing only on the top-three outputs.

Pseudo Log-Likelihood Scoring (PLL). This method evaluates the likelihood of a sentence under a masked language model by summing the log probabilities of each token, conditioned on the rest of the sentence. In bias detection, PLL compares scores for paired sentences, one stereotypical and one anti-stereotypical, to identify biases. A higher PLL score for the stereotypical sentence indicates the model’s bias toward that stereotype [54].

Categorical Bias (CB) Score. Categorical Bias score [55] measures ethnic bias in bidirectional Transformer (BERT) [56] embeddings by calculating the average cosine similarity between embeddings of ethnic group names (e.g., names associated with different ethnicities) and context-specific target words (e.g., positive or negative attributes). By evaluating these associations across categories, CB score provides a quantitative measure of how strongly ethnic biases are encoded in the model.

CrowS-Pairs Score. The CrowS-Pairs score [57] evaluates bias in masked language models using a challenge dataset of sentence pairs. Each pair consists of two sentences that differ only in their bias, with one reflecting a stereotype and the other being neutral or anti-stereotypical. The score is calculated based on the model’s preference for one sentence over the other, typically measured through likelihood or probability assigned to the sentences. A higher score indicates stronger bias encoded in the language model, providing a direct evaluation of biases such as gender, race, or religion in model outputs.

Winogender Schemas. Winogender Schemas developed by Rudinger et al. [17], are designed to measure gender bias in coreference resolution systems. Authors extend the Winograd Schema Challenge, which tests a system’s ability to resolve pronoun references, by incorporating gender-neutral contexts to expose biases in NLP models.

Co-occurrence Bias Score. Bordia and Bowman [58] proposed a metric to measure the gender bias, which can be expressed as the probability of a word occurring in context with gendered words. The distribution of the bias is analysed by evaluating mean absolute bias and deviation in bias scores for each context word in each of the generated corpora. Similarly, Chaloner et al. [13] quantified bias based on co-occurrence of words. Authors hypothesised that words occurring in close proximity to a particular gender in the training data are prone to be more biased towards that gender during testing.

Authors also proposed a clustering method that discovers new gender-associated word categories, the induced topics seem to mix harmless gender-associated words (like people names) with more obviously harmful gender-biased words.

4.3 Prompt or Template-based Approaches

Prompt or template based approaches test for bias by analysing how a model responds to structured prompts, revealing potential biases in the way the model generates or completes sentences. Models are prompted through a set of pre-defined templates, or patterns, that capture specific types of bias or stereotypes. The templates contain slots that are filled through selection from a set of predefined demographic target terms during evaluation. For instance, a template could be [PERSON] *is walking* where [PERSON] is systematically substituted with names associated with different demographic groups [25]. By analysing the differences in the model’s responses to these substitutions, the presence and degree of bias can be measured [21]. These techniques use various methods like counterfactual or mask sentences, to detect bias in the model’s generated text and help us to test the model’s ability to generate fair and neutral responses to prompts.

Counterfactual-based methods, where attributes in the sentence are swapped to create counterfactuals (e.g., replacing John with Mary in John is a doctor). If the model generates different responses based on the gender or race of the subject, it may indicate bias. Similarly, masked sentence approaches are pivotal in assessing biases within contextualised word representations. These methods involve creating sentence templates (e.g., CrowS-Pairs [57]) with masked tokens such as [MASK] is a doctor), allowing models to predict the masked words. By analysing how the model fills in the blank (e.g., man or woman), we can identify if it is biased toward a certain gender or stereotype.

Sheng et al. [59] introduced a template-based approach that uses structured sentence templates, such as The [demographic group] worked as a [profession] to systematically probe how models generate text about specific groups (e.g., woman or man). These templates reveal stereotypical patterns in the outputs, reflecting potential biases in the model’s training data. The *regard score* complements this approach by measuring the social perception conveyed in the generated text, categorising outputs as positive, negative, or neutral. Huang et al. [60] generated counterfactual inputs by altering sensitive attributes (e.g., country, occupation, and name) in conditioning contexts and analysed the sentiment of the generated text. Shen et al. [61] worked on uncovering biases in conversational recommendation systems powered by LLMs. By creating input templates with variations in non-preferential entities (e.g., names or attributes), the authors evaluated how these changes affect recommendations. By comparing outputs across different attribute values, they measured bias using individual and group fairness metrics. Goldfarb-Tarrant et al. [62] focused on identifying unforeseen biases in LLMs using counterfactual reasoning. The authors proposed generating counterfactual examples through input perturbations and analysing model responses in these hypothetical scenarios.

Kurita et al. [53] constructed sentences with masked tokens representing attributes (e.g., professions) and targets (e.g., gender pronouns). By examining the model’s predictions for these masked tokens, they assessed biases in the representations. Ahn and Ohn [55] analysed ethnic biases in monolingual BERT models across multiple languages. They developed the Categorical Bias Score, a metric that uses masked sentence templates to measure bias. Likewise, Hutchinson et al. [30] explored how the BERT model represents phrases mentioning persons with disabilities. They adopted a template-based fill-in-the-blank analysis. Given a query sentence with a missing word, BERT predicts a ranked list of words to fill in the blank. Authors also analysed how the top ranked words predicted by BERT change when different disability phrases are used in the query sentence. Zalkikar

and Chandra [63] proposed an iterative masking experiment to evaluate social biases in masked language models. Their method assessed the quality of the models' predictions by iteratively masking tokens and analysing the model's performance, providing insights into biases encoded in the model. Lastly, Koksal et al. [64] introduced LABDet, a language-agnostic framework proposed for evaluating and detecting biases in pre-trained language models using a systematic template-based probing approach. This framework assesses biases across languages using generalisable templates, such as this [nationality] person is [adjective], which can be adapted to various linguistic and cultural contexts. By replacing placeholders like [nationality] and [adjective] with diverse values, the system probes how language models associate characteristics with specific groups. LABDet operates by training a classifier on top of a frozen pretrained language model representations to predict sentiment while explicitly excluding nationality information. This setup allows for probing the influence of nationality-related features on model predictions and identifies consistent bias patterns tied to historical and political contexts.

4.4 Metrics for Behavioural Probing

LLMs can generate outputs that are untruthful, toxic, or simply not helpful to the user. Behavioural probing assesses bias by examining how models respond to specific prompts, focusing on user interaction-based biases.

Sycophancy Metric. This metric measures how often a model agrees with user inputs, even if they are incorrect or biased. For instance, when a user alternates between liking and disliking an argument, the model shifts its stance accordingly, validating user preferences rather than providing an unbiased response. This behaviour reveals models' tendency to mirror user inputs, potentially reinforcing biases. For example, in ChatGPT-4, the model may apologise and change a correct answer if questioned, introducing errors. The frequency of sycophantic responses varies across models, with some like LLaMA 2 displaying higher rates and Claude 1.3 wrongly admitting mistakes on 98% of questions. The study has shown that the user suggesting an incorrect answer can reduce accuracy by up to 27% in LLaMA 2. Moreover, the user suggesting the correct answer tends to improve accuracy. AI assistants tend to modify their answers to agree with user beliefs, even if weakly expressed [33].

The following metrics can help in understanding the extent to which biasing features affect both the performance and the transparency of LLMs [65].

Accuracy Drop. This metric quantifies the decrease in model performance when biasing features are introduced in the inputs. For instance, the study reports an accuracy reduction of up to 36% across 13 tasks from the Big-Bench Hard suite [66] when models like GPT-3.5 and Claude 1.0 are subjected to biased inputs.

Faithfulness of Explanations. This metric evaluates how accurately the model's chain-of-thoughts (CoT) [67] explanations reflect its actual reasoning process. It measures whether the explanations genuinely reflect the factors influencing the model's answers. Models often generate plausible yet misleading explanations that fail to mention the impact of biasing features, indicating a lack of faithfulness.

4.5 Assessing Performance Disparities

This section reviews the approaches used to identify inequities in model outputs across different demographic groups, ensuring fairness and minimising harm.

Sap et al. [24] analysed how insensitivity to dialect can lead to discrimination against minorities, even without explicit mentions. To do so, the authors inferred dialect using a lexical detector of words associated with African American English dialect (AAE) or white-aligned English. To quantify the racial bias that can arise during the annotation process, the Pearson correlation between toxicity annotations and dialect probabilities were investigated. Authors reported differences in rates of false positives between AAE and White-aligned dialect groups for models trained on two datasets. Authors proposed dialect and race priming as ways to reduce the racial bias in annotation, showing that when annotators are made explicitly aware of an AAE tweet’s dialect they are significantly less likely to label the tweet as offensive. A speech recognition system is biased if it has higher error rates for African American dialects, meaning that systems perform less well for those speakers [68].

Al Kuwatly et al. [69] investigated the effect of the annotator’s demographics on the quality of resulting classifiers. They used the annotators’ demographic information (e.g., gender, age, education and native English speaker) present in the Wulczyn personal attacks dataset [70]. They found no differences between the two genders. However, models trained on native English speakers’ annotations outperformed the ones for non-native speakers in terms of F1 score and sensitivity. Similar differences were observed across both groups for age and education.

Classifier-based metrics use an auxiliary model to evaluate bias, toxicity, or sentiment in the generated text. Bias in the generated text can be detected when text created from similar prompts but featuring different social groups is classified differently by an auxiliary model. For example, gender bias is quantified by analysing the difference in true positive rates of gender in classification outcomes in De-Artega et al. [7].

Gender Bias Evaluation Test-sets (GBETs). Standard test sets in NLP fail to measure the gender bias in models. These test sets themselves contain biases (such as containing more male references than female references), so evaluation on them might not reveal biases. The goal of designing GBETs introduced by Sun et al. [71] is to provide a standardised dataset to streamline research and allow them to measure biases present in users’ algorithm. GBETs use differences in values of the probing concept (e.g., occupation) or prediction accuracies relating to the probing concept between gender-swapped data points to measure bias.

Gender swapped GBETs. Gender swapping was performed by replacing every male related word with its female equivalent and vice versa. A system free from bias must give the same performance on both the male and female swapped test sets. The difference in score here acts as a proxy for the gender bias in the system [71]. For example, Rudinger et al. [17] and Zhao et al. [72] independently designed GBETs based on Winograd Schemas for coreference resolution.

Perturbation sensitivity analysis (PSA). Perturbation, where a reference to a real-world entity is replaced by a reference to another real-world entity of the same type (e.g., a person name replaced with another person name) has been used in many studies. Prabhakaran et al. [20] introduced PSA, a general-purpose evaluation framework that detects unintended biases in NLP models around named entities mentioned in text. PSA measures the extent to which a model prediction is sensitive to such perturbations and is calculated by using a set of (unannotated) sentences from the target domain and a set of names (of the same entity type) that the perturbations are performed over. Other metrics in the literature to quantify possible performance disparities are:

Predictive Parity Metric. Hutchinson and Mitchell [73] measured the difference in precision for a privileged and non-privileged group using the predictive parity metric. This metric measures fairness by evaluating whether the model’s predicted outcomes have similar positive values across different demographic groups, ensuring that predictions for each group are equally reliable. It focuses on balancing the proportion of true positive predictions within each group, highlighting potential biases

in model performance.

Performance Gap Metric. These metrics measure difference in performance across different demographic splits of the data. Goldfarb-Tarrant et al. [74] examined performance gaps in both precision and in recall for broad coverage. For different applications, false negatives may be more harmful, for others false positives may be. False negatives permit abuse of minority populations that are targets of hate speech. This work quantifies bias using identity terms affected by the false positive bias are disproportionately used in toxic comments in the training dataset of Dixon et al. [35]. The authors created a set of 51 common identity terms and looked for similar disproportionate representations.

False Positive Rate Difference Metric. Yao et al. [75] used F1-scores on source domain and target domain test sets, and also the hate-speech classifiers on the Identity Phrase Template Test [35] (where 50% of them are toxic). Unintended biases were measured for identity phrases by computing the False Positive Rate Difference metric. A smaller value of this metric suggests that the model is less biased.

5 Debiasing

Debiasing or bias mitigation is crucial in AI systems to make models fairer, enhance accuracy in their predictions and recommendations and maintain public trust [76]. It helps prevent discriminatory outcomes in applications like toxicity detection, where biases can lead to uneven targeting or overlooking of certain groups. Moreover, effective bias mitigation supports the creation of more equitable and reliable technology, preventing harm and protecting marginalised communities.

The bias mitigation process in model development flows through three main phases: In the pre-processing phase, bias reduction begins before training by modifying or augmenting the training data, aiming to minimise bias in the dataset itself. During the training phase, additional bias mitigation techniques are applied as the model is trained or fine-tuned, ensuring it doesn't internalise biased associations. Finally, in the post-processing phase, adjustments are made to the model's outputs at inference time, preventing biased content in real-time predictions. This three step approach helps manage and mitigate bias throughout the model's lifecycle.

5.1 Pre-processing Debiasing

In the pre-processing phase, bias mitigation modifies training data before it is used to shape model learning. Techniques include data augmentation, data filtering and reweighting, which removes biased data and assigns higher importance to minority instances. Data generation fills representation gaps by creating new examples, while instruction tuning adjusts prompts to guide the model toward less biased outputs. Finally, projection-based mitigation debiases word embeddings by projecting biased associations away, ensuring fairer representations of gender, race, and other attributes.

Data Augmentation. Data augmentation enhances training data by introducing counterfactual examples to balance representations. Lu et al. [77] introduced Counterfactual Data Augmentation (CDA), to reduce gender bias by generating counterfactual instances to balance gender representation. This involves substituting gender specific words, such as he and she to construct novel sentences. Similarly, Park et al. [78] augmented the training data by identifying male entities and swapping them with equivalent female entities and vice versa. This simple method removes correlation between gender and classification decision and has proven to be effective for correcting gender biases in coreference resolution task. Maudslay et al. [79] enhanced this approach with Counterfactual Data

Substitution (CDS), which assigns probabilities to these changes, aiming for more realistic modifications. CDS reduces gender bias by replacing gender-informative names in the dataset with gender neutral names and which aims to effectively reduce gender bias. CDS is a variant of CDA in which potentially biased text is randomly substituted to avoid duplication, and uses Names Intervention, a novel name-pairing technique that vastly increases the number of words being treated.

Data Balancing. Data balancing is a method to ensure that different groups or categories in a dataset are represented equally or proportionally. This approach aims to reduce biases that arise from imbalanced data, where certain groups may dominate the dataset, leading to skewed model predictions and decision-making. By re-sampling (oversampling underrepresented groups or under-sampling overrepresented ones) or augmenting data, balancing helps create a more equitable dataset for training models. Goldfarb-Tarrant et al. [74] modified data distributions to test whether balancing reduces biases in downstream tasks like coreference resolution.

Data Reweighting. Data reweighting involves assigning different importance or weights to training samples, prioritising underrepresented or unbiased data, to guide the model toward fairer and more equitable learning. Orgad and Belinkov [80] used data reweighting to mitigate bias by down-weighting samples that the main model predicts with high confidence, as these often rely on spurious correlations. This approach, guided by an auxiliary model, avoids using demographic labels and encourages learning from more informative, unbiased examples. Similarly, Han et al. [81] applied data reweighting to ensure fair representation by adjusting sample weights based on their demographic attributes. This helps emphasise under-represented groups during training, reducing disparities and enhancing fairness in predictions.

Data Filtering. Data filtering refers to the process of removing or excluding specific data points or documents from a training dataset that are identified as biased, harmful, or misaligned with desired ethical standards. Ngo et al. [82] introduced a data filtering technique aimed at reducing biases in language models. This method involves using a pretrained language model to assess the likelihood of specific phrases within documents. By calculating the conditional log-likelihood of these phrases, the approach identifies and filters out documents containing potentially harmful content from the training dataset. The study demonstrated that models trained on this filtered data exhibit a lower propensity to generate harmful text, with only a marginal decrease in performance on standard language modelling benchmarks compared to unfiltered baselines.

Prompt Modification. This method involves altering the input prompts given to a language model to guide its outputs toward more neutral or fair representations, reducing the likelihood of generating biased or harmful text. Venkit et al. [83] employed adversarial triggering, a technique that modifies prompts to mitigate nationality biases. This method involves incorporating positive trigger words, such as hopeful and hard-working, into prompts to influence the model’s output towards more favourable and less biased narratives about various nationalities.

Projection-based Mitigation. These methods mainly involve manipulating embeddings by projecting them onto or away from specific directions or subspaces. For example, Dev et al. [84] introduced a bias mitigation approach, OSCaR, which identifies two subspaces within word embeddings: one representing a specific bias (e.g., gender) and another representing a concept (e.g., occupation). By applying a graded rotation, OSCaR orthogonalises these subspaces, effectively disentangling biased associations without removing the concepts themselves. This approach aims to reduce bias while preserving the semantic integrity of the embeddings, ensuring that essential information is retrained for downstream tasks. Schramowski et al. [85] explored mitigating ethical and moral biases inherent in LLMs. They identified a moral direction within the embedding space of these models, which reflects

societal norms and biases present in the training data. By computing this direction using methods like PCA, they proposed adjusting the embeddings to align with desired ethical standards. This approach enables the attenuation or prevention of toxic generation in LLMs, guiding them toward generating more normative and ethically aligned text outputs.

5.2 Training Debiasing

During training, several techniques are applied to reduce bias in the model and improve fairness. Fine-tuning, one of the most effective methods, involves updating a pre-trained model (e.g., [56]) with bias-focused data and adjusting specific layers, helping to mitigate harmful associations. Modifying the loss function introduces fairness objectives that penalise biased outputs and prevent overfitting to biased patterns. Additionally, training paradigms like contrastive, reinforcement, and adversarial learning are used to avoid biased associations with social groups. Techniques such as parameter updating and filtering, further refine the model by retraining or neutralising specific components, saving computational resources while enhancing fairness. Finally, human-in-the-loop oversight enables human reviewers to catch subtle biases undetectable by automated methods, ensuring alignment with ethical standards.

Bias Mitigation via Training Optimisations. Training optimisation approaches address biases during the model’s learning process by refining training techniques. Key methods include loss function modification, adding fairness constraints and penalties; dropout regularisation, deactivating neurons to reduce reliance on biased features; adversarial training; and parameter updating and filtering, selectively adjusting or freezing parameters for fairness. These strategies ensure models learn fairer representations while maintaining performance.

Loss Function Modifications. Additional terms are added to penalise biased behaviour or encourage fairness. Li et al. [86] presented an adversarial training-inspired two-stage debiasing model using Contrastive learning with Continuous Prompt Augmentation to mitigate social biases in PLMs’ encoding. Huang et al. [60] proposed a three-step curriculum training using distance between the embeddings as a fairness loss to reduce sentiment bias. Bordia and Bowman [58] proposed a regularisation loss term for reducing gender bias, to minimise the projection of encoder-trained embeddings onto an embedding space that encodes gender. The authors trained the word embeddings from scratch and debias them while the language model is trained. In addition, Meissner et al. [87] implemented an ablation experiment where the debiasing loss is replaced with the standard cross-entropy loss, using the same pruning parameters. Liu et al. [88] introduced a regularisation term that decreases the distance between the embedding of a gender or race word and that of its counterpart into the loss function. For a similar work, see Huang et al. [60]. Likewise, Zhao et al. [18] proposed a loss function modification to mitigate gender bias during training. An additional term is added to the loss function to equalise the probabilities of male and female gendered words, promoting balanced gender representations in the model’s outputs.

Dropout Regularisation. Dropout is a regularisation technique applied during the training phase, where a fraction of neurons is randomly deactivated in each training iteration. This promotes generalisation and prevents the model from over-relying on specific features in the training data. By incorporating dropout, the study [25] demonstrated a reduction in the amplification of gendered correlations, highlighting its effectiveness as a bias mitigation strategy. Dasu et al. [89] proposed NeuFair, a framework that employs adversarial learning to identify and drop neurons contributing to biased predictions, thereby improving model fairness without significantly compromising performance.

Parameter Updating & Filtering. These approaches focus on refining language models by efficiently updating specific parameters and incorporating mechanisms to filter out undesirable biases during training or fine-tuning. These methods aim to balance computational efficiency with effective debiasing, ensuring that models maintain performance while reducing stereotypical and harmful biases in their representations or outputs. For example, Agarwal et al. [90] introduced PEFTDebias, a parameter-efficient fine tuning (PEFT) method designed to mitigate biases in large foundation models. PEFTDebias operates in two phases: (i) an upstream phase, which employs counterfactual data augmentation to acquire debiasing parameters along a specific bias axis; and (ii) a downstream phase, which incorporates these debiasing parameters into the model and freezes them during fine-tuning. By targeting specific bias dimensions and using efficient parameter updates, PEFTDebias significantly reduces biases while minimising computational costs. Wang and Demberg [91] incorporated multiple objectives to reduce stereotypes while preserving model performance. The approach leverages PEFT methods to minimise computational overhead while addressing bias. During training, the model is guided by additional debiasing objectives, which explicitly target stereotypical biases encoded in the language model’s representations. This ensures that the model not only learns language patterns but also internalises fairness constraints. The multi-objective framework allows for a balanced trade-off between debiasing and maintaining high quality output, making this an effective and scalable solution for mitigating biases in large-scale language models.

Adversarial Debiasing. Adversarial training or debiasing, is a technique that incorporates adversarial objectives to reduce biases in machine learning models, including LLMs. It involves training a base model to perform its task while simultaneously training an adversary model to predict sensitive attributes, such as gender or race, from the base model’s outputs. The base model minimises its task-specific loss while maximising the adversary’s error, effectively removing bias-inducing information from its predictions. For example, Ernst et al. [92] proposed an adversarial debiasing method, which involves training the model to minimise task-specific loss while an adversary attempts to predict protected attributes, encouraging the model to produce unbiased outputs. Similarly, Han et al. [93] introduced an adversarial learning approach that uses diverse adversaries to mitigate biases in language models. By incorporating multiple adversarial objectives, the method aims to reduce model bias more effectively during training.

Human-in-the-loop. These methods involve humans identifying biases in models, which are then used to fine-tune them. Yao et al. [75] refined language models for a target domain by collecting human provided explanations to identify spurious bias patterns in model outputs and reduce bias in the models. Dinan et al. [94] employed a human-in-the-loop bias mitigation approach through an iterative *build it, break it, fix it* strategy. This approach involves humans interacting with the dialogue system to identify and exploit its vulnerability (break it), followed by refining the model to address these weaknesses (fix it). This iterative process enhances the model’s robustness against adversarial human attacks by continuously incorporating human feedback to mitigate biases and improve safety. Building on the iterative human-in-the-loop framework that focuses on identifying and addressing vulnerabilities through adversarial feedback, the next approach refines this concept by leveraging human feedback during training to systematically align model outputs with desired behaviours and mitigate biases effectively. Ouyang et al. [95] focused on bias mitigation using a technique central to the InstructGPT model. This approach employs reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF), where human evaluators rank model outputs based on their alignment with ethical and instructional guidelines. These rankings are used to train a reward model that guides the language model to prioritise responses aligned with human values, effectively mitigating biases by continuously incorporating human oversight during the fine-tuning process.

Online Skewness Mitigation. Manela et al. [96] introduced an Online Skewness Mitigation technique to address gender bias in language models. This method involves normalising the probability of a masked pronoun being predicted as a certain gender within an occupational context by dividing it by the prior probability of choosing that gender in non-occupational context. By adjusting the model’s token prediction probabilities during training or fine-tuning, this technique ensures that gender pronouns are distributed more equitably, reducing stereotypical biases in various contexts.

Few-Shot Debiasing with Fine-Tuning. Thakur et al. [97] demonstrated the effectiveness of fine-tuning pre-trained language models using small, debiased datasets to significantly reduce gender bias. Their approach leverages several established debiasing techniques, including Dropout [25], which acts as a regularisation method to mitigate bias; and Counterfactual Data Augmentation [98], which creates balanced datasets by generating counterfactual examples.

Projection-based Mitigation. Word embeddings, while effective for capturing semantic relationships, often perpetuate gender biases present in their training corpora. To address this, various projection-based mitigation techniques have been developed, focusing on modifying embeddings to reduce biases while maintaining their semantic utility [14]. A notable framework is Debiaswe, introduced by Bolukbasi et al. [15], which adjusts the vector deviations between gendered and gender-neutral terms. This technique identifies a gender subspace in the embedding space and removes gender-related components from gender-neutral words while ensuring gendered terms retain their relationships. GloVe, a widely used pre-trained embedding, serves as a baseline representing non-debiased embeddings. Building on this, Bolukbasi proposed Hard-GloVe, which applies the Debiaswe principles to GloVe embeddings. Zhao et al. [72] extended this work with GN-GloVe, a gender neutral version of GloVe designed to eliminate gender stereotypes. Similarly, Kaneko and Bollegala [99] introduced GP-GloVe, a gender-preserving version that balances semantic relationships and debiasing, ensuring utility for downstream applications. Zhao et al. [100] addressed gender bias in ELMo embeddings. The authors applied two primary approaches: (i) hard-debiasing, which involves identifying a gender subspace within the embedding space and neutralising gender-specific words by projecting them onto a subspace orthogonal to the gender direction, reducing encoded gender information; and (ii) data augmentation, which balances gender representation by swapping gendered words in the training data. This augmentation creates gender swapped sentences that help the model learn more equitable associations with professions and attributes.

Large scale pretraining datasets, while powerful, carry significant social risks due to their potential to amplify harmful stereotypes and propagate biases related to gender, race, religion, and other social constructs. Bender et al. [36] and Liang et al. [101] highlighted how these biases manifest not only in representational stereotypes but also in ethical and moral norms embedded in language models, which can influence decision-making systems with undesired consequences. These risks underscore the importance of bias mitigation techniques like those described above, which aim to make large-scale models safer and more equitable.

5.3 Post-processing Debiasing

In the post-processing phase, bias mitigation techniques aim to correct the model’s outputs during real-time interaction to ensure fairness and accuracy.

Output Rewriting. Output rewriting aims at mitigating biases in generated text by modifying outputs to align with fairness and neutrality standards. This approach involves transforming biased or impolite language into more neutral or polite forms without altering the original intent. By focusing on the final output, it allows for the correction of biases introduced during text generation, enhan-

cing the fairness and inclusivity of language models. For example, Wang et al. [102] developed a dataset specifically for polite language rewriting, addressing the challenge of transforming impolite or offensive sentences into polite expressions. Similarly, Amrhein et al. [103] proposed a method to debias text by leveraging biased models to generate gender-fair rewrites. Their approach involves creating pseudo training data through machine translation models, which generate gender-biased text from gender-fair text via round-trip translation. This enables the training of a rewriting model that can transform biased outputs into gender-neutral language, effectively reducing gender bias in text generation. Similarly, Majumber et al. [104] introduced InterFair, a debiasing framework that utilises natural language feedback to guide the rewriting of biased model outputs. By incorporating human-in-the-loop feedback, the system learns to adjust its predictions and explanations to be more fair and interpretable. Additionally, Shu et al. [105] introduced RewriteLM, an instruction-tuned LLM designed for text rewriting, with a focus on cross-sentence transformations and bias mitigation as a post-processing approach. By fine-tuning on diverse rewriting instructions from Wikipedia edits and public corpora, it reduces the perpetuation of biases inherent in homogeneous datasets. Utilising reinforcement learning with a reward model, RewriteLM prioritises unbiased, high-quality outputs by balancing content preservation and linguistic variability.

Post-hoc. This approach is applied after a model has generated its outputs. It involves analysing and modifying the model’s predictions to reduce biases, ensuring that the final outputs align with fairness and neutrality standards. By focusing on the outputs rather than the model’s internal parameters, post-hoc filtering offers a flexible and model-agnostic solution to bias mitigation.

REFINE-LM. REFINE-LM is a bias mitigation technique introduced by Qureshi et al. [106], which employs reinforcement learning to address stereotypes in language models. Unlike traditional methods that require extensive retraining or data pre-processing, REFINE-LM operates as a post-hoc filtering mechanism, making it adaptable to various biases without significant computational overhead. By training a model on top of the word probability distribution of a language model, REFINE-LM reduces stereotypical biases while preserving the model’s performance.

Iterative Null Space Projection (INLP). Shen et al. [61] proposed INLP, a method that systematically removes bias by iteratively training a linear classifier to predict bias-related attributes (such as gender) and projecting embeddings into the null space of this classifier. This ensures that the embeddings are less sensitive to bias-associated features while retaining their effectiveness for classification tasks.

General Bias Direction Debiasing (GBDD). This method aimed at mitigating biases in word embedding spaces. It identifies the bias subspace (i.e., a set of dimensions in the embedding space that encode stereotypical associations) and adjusts the embeddings to minimise the influence of these biased dimensions. By neutralising or removing the bias subspace, this method preserves the core semantic relationships in the embeddings while reducing unfair or stereotypical correlations [107].

Self-Debias. Self-Debias [108] enables pre-trained language models to autonomously identify and mitigate biases in their outputs. This method involves a two-step process: first, the model performs self-diagnosis by analysing its own outputs to detect biases using diagnostic prompts, and second, it applies self-debiasing by conditioning its text generation on descriptions of undesired behaviours to avoid producing biased language. Without requiring retraining or external data, Self-Debias leverages the model’s internal knowledge, providing an efficient and adaptable solution to reduce biases in NLP applications.

Attract-Repel Algorithm. Goldfarb-Tarrant et al. [74] adopted the Attract-Repel algorithm [109] to enhance the semantic quality of pre-trained word vectors by integrating external lexical constraints. By applying constraints that define equal relationships between gendered word pairs (e.g., man and

woman) and ensuring that gender-neutral words (e.g., doctor, nurse) are equidistant from these pairs, Attract Repel can adjust embeddings to reduce gender bias. This process involves attracting synonymous words and repelling antonymous ones, effectively reshaping the vector space to diminish biased associations.

DEXPERTS. In DEXPERTS [110], bias mitigation is achieved through adjusting token probabilities during text generation. An expert model promotes desirable outputs (e.g., non-toxic text), while an anti-expert model suppresses undesirable content (e.g., toxicity). By dynamically balancing the influence of these models, DEXPERTS steers the base language model’s outputs toward reduced bias and improved fairness, all without requiring retraining.

Sent-Debias. Sent-Debias [29, 111], a method designed to reduce social biases in sentence-level representations generated by language models. It identifies a bias subspace within the embedding space that captures dimensions associated with specific biases, such as gender, race, or societal stereotypes. Using predefined sets of biased words, the algorithm computes the direction of these biases and modifies sentence embeddings by projecting them onto the orthogonal complement of the bias subspace. This effectively neutralises biased associations while preserving semantic information. As a post-processing method, Sent-Debias is applied to pre-trained models without retraining or fine-tuning, making it suitable for a wide range of applications.

Chain-of-thought (CoT). Chain-of-Thought prompting is a method in NLP where LLMs are guided to articulate their reasoning process step-by-step before producing a final response. By breaking down complex problems into a sequence of logical and interpretable steps, CoT prompting enhances the model’s ability to reason, reducing errors and improving its performance on tasks requiring multi-step thinking. Kaneko et al. [112] leveraged CoT prompting as a bias mitigation technique. By requiring the model to explicitly reason through its decision step-by-step, such as labeling words as feminine, masculine, or gender-neutral in occupational contexts, CoT prompting reduces the influence of unexpected biases on the model’s outputs.

LLM Behaviour Modification. LLMs can be prompted to perform a range of NLP tasks, given some examples of the task as input. However, these models often express unintended behaviours like making up facts, generating biased or toxic text, or simply not following user instructions [36]. There are many ways to change the generation behaviour of language models and mitigate the generated bias by LLMs. LLM behaviour modification approaches adjust the outputs of LLMs to align with ethical, social, or functional standards, such as reducing biases or improving fairness.

AXOLOTL [113] is a framework that interacts with LLMs via public APIs to identify and reduce biases in generated outputs. The method employs a three-step process resembling zero-shot learning, enabling models to self-debias without extensive computational resources. Yifei et al. [114] presented a soft projection method to identify and remove bias subspaces in LLMs like BERT and GPT. This approach modifies the decision threshold or probabilities associated with the model’s predictions, effectively reducing bias in the final outcomes.

Kadhe et al. [115] introduced FairSISA, which creates an ensemble of models trained on disjoint data shards. They identified that unlearning can inadvertently reduce fairness in LLMs. To counteract this, authors designed three approaches. These include threshold adjustment, which modifies decision thresholds to balance predictions; probability calibration, which aligns output probabilities with actual outcomes to enhance fairness; and an optimal fair predictor, to satisfy fairness constraints while optimising ensemble predictions.

Solaiman and Dennison [116] fine-tuned LLMs on a small, value-targeted dataset, called, a Process for Adapting Language Models to Society (PALMS) with Values-Targeted Datasets, an iterative process to significantly change model behaviour by crafting and fine-tuning on a dataset that reflects

a predetermined set of target values. This dataset improves the model’s ability to adhere to these values on a question answering task.

6 Bias Evaluation Resources

Bias evaluation involves assessing how language models perform across different contexts, focusing on fairness, exclusivity, and whether they generate biased or harmful content. This assessment uses datasets designed to expose biases. For example, CrowS-Pairs [57] assesses stereotypical associations in categories like race, gender and religion; BOLD evaluates bias in open-ended demographic content; StereoSet [23] measures biases in gender, race, and professions; and ToxiGen focuses on toxic language, particularly toward marginalised communities.

Alongside datasets, tools like the PerspectiveAPI flag toxic language, AI Fairness 360 provides fairness metrics, and FairSeq can be used for evaluating sequence-to-sequence models. For hands-on-evaluations, Python libraries and Hugging Face’s evaluation platform which includes metrics like HONEST for fairness, or TOXICITY for harmful language detection can also be used for the bias analysis. This section reviews benchmark datasets and tools for evaluating bias.

6.1 Datasets

In this section, we review benchmark and evaluation datasets used to measure various types of bias (e.g., gender, stereotypical, intersectional, toxicity, model behaviour, etc.) in LLMs.

Gender bias arises when language models perpetuate stereotypes or unequal representations based on gender. Addressing this bias is crucial for ensuring fairness in applications like coreference resolution, and text generation. Gender bias can be evaluated using the following datasets:

BiasInBios¹. A dataset containing occupation-based gender stereotypes, designed to evaluate biases in language models and assess their impact on downstream tasks (e.g., occupation classification) [7].

BUG². BUG, a large-scale bias dataset with 108,000 sentences curated for analysing gender bias in machine translation and coreference resolution tasks. It is built using lexical-syntactic patterns to capture gendered contexts [117].

CALM³. This dataset is used to evaluate gender and racial bias across multiple NLP tasks (e.g., question answering, natural language inference). It utilises diverse templates for consistent and balanced assessments [118].

GAP Coreference dataset⁴. A gender-balanced evaluation dataset containing 8,908 coreference-labelled pairs of ambiguous pronouns and antecedent names. It is designed to test gender bias in coreference resolution tasks and ensure fairness in model predictions [39].

MDGender⁵. A multi-dimensional dataset that dissects gender bias into pragmatic dimensions such as the speaker’s gender, the listener’s gender, and the gender of the individual being discussed. This dataset provides a nuanced framework for understanding and addressing gender bias in text [119].

¹<https://github.com/microsoft/biosbias>

²<https://github.com/SLAB-NLP/BUG>

³<https://huggingface.co/datasets/vipulgupta/CALM>

⁴<https://github.com/google-research-datasets/gap-coreference?tab=readme-ov-file>

⁵https://huggingface.co/datasets/md_gender_bias

WinoBias⁶. A dataset based on Winograd-schema style sentences, tailored to examine gender bias in coreference resolution. It includes occupations paired with gendered pronouns to test for stereotypical and counter-stereotypical associations [18].

Winogender Schemas⁷. A benchmark designed to test gender bias in coreference resolution using pairs of sentences that differ only by the pronoun’s gender. It evaluates whether models associate genders equally with occupations and other roles [17].

WinoQueer⁸. This dataset measures biases against LGBTQ+ individuals, providing 45,540 sentences structures across 11 templates. It focuses on detecting anti-LGBTQ+ biases in language models [27].

Intersectional bias occurs when language models reflect combined biases across multiple social dimensions, such as race, gender and profession. This type of bias highlights the need to evaluate how overlapping identities are represented in model behaviour. It can be evaluated using the following datasets:

HolisticBias⁹. A dataset for evaluating bias in conversations, using demographic identity language combined with sentence templates. It addresses intersectional biases across 13 demographic categories including gender, race and religion [22].

Multilingual Intrinsic Bias (MIB) Dataset¹⁰. A dataset that assess biases in multilingual settings, incorporating occupation and gender seed words across English, Spanish, German, and French. It highlights biases influenced by linguistic and cultural properties of different languages [51].

Bias Benchmark for Question Answering (BBQ)¹¹. A dataset focused on measuring social biases in question answering, this dataset includes 58,492 examples covering nine dimensions such as race, gender, and socioeconomic status, tailored for U.S. English-speaking contexts [120]

PANDA (Perturbation Augmentation NLP Dataset)¹². A dataset for evaluating intersectional biases through perturbations in text. It focuses on how language models respond to subtle changes in sentences while maintaining semantic meaning. PANDA tests models’ robustness to demographic-related bias in diverse contexts.

Stereotypical biases in language models reinforce harmful generalisations about social groups, affecting fairness and equity in downstream tasks. Evaluating these biases is critical to prevent discriminatory outputs. The following are datasets commonly used to analyse stereotypical biases:

AdvPromptSet¹³. AdvPromptSet contains 197,628 adversarial prompts designed to test for fairness and bias across sensitive demographic identity groups. It evaluates model behaviour against various prompts of varying toxicity levels [121].

Bias in Open-ended Language Generation Dataset (BOLD)¹⁴. A dataset created to measure fairness in open-ended language generation. It covers domains such as professions, gender, race, religion, and political ideologies, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of bias in generative models [122].

⁶https://huggingface.co/datasets/wino_bias

⁷<https://github.com/rudinger/winogender-schemas>

⁸<https://github.com/katyfelkner/winoqueer>

⁹https://github.com/facebookresearch/ResponsibleNLP/tree/main/holistic_bias

¹⁰<https://github.com/MSR-LIT/MultilingualBias>

¹¹<https://github.com/nyu-ml/BQ>

¹²<https://huggingface.co/datasets/facebook/panda>

¹³<https://github.com/facebookresearch/ResponsibleNLP/tree/main/AdvPromptSet>

¹⁴<https://github.com/amazon-science/bold>

CrowS-Pairs¹⁵. A dataset designed to test the tendency of models to perpetuate stereotypes across nine dimensions, including gender, race and religion. It uses minimally different sentence pairs to evaluate bias in masked language models [57].

HONEST¹⁶. A multilingual dataset that provides 420 cloze-based sentences to evaluate gender stereotypes in English, Italian, French, Portuguese, Spanish, and Romanian. Each sentence tests the tendency of models to complete prompts with stereotypical language [123].

SemBias¹⁷. A word analogy dataset used to measure biases in word embeddings by testing their ability to produce gendered or biased analogies. It is specifically aimed at evaluating gender-related biases in embeddings [72].

StereoSet¹⁸. A dataset comprising 1,700 tests to evaluate stereotypical biases in language models across race, gender, religion, and profession. It measures whether models reinforce stereotypes through intra-sentence and inter-sentence contexts [23].

WinoGrande¹⁹. A large-scale dataset inspired by the Winograd Schema Challenge, containing 44,000 sentence pairs. It is formulated as a fill-in-the-blank task with binary options, requiring common-sense reasoning. WinoGrande reduces dataset-specific biases and tests stereotypical associations [124].

Toxicity and hate speech in language models can harm users by generating or amplifying offensive, hateful, or harmful content. These biases must be addressed to ensure safety and inclusivity in AI systems. Listed below are datasets that can assist in evaluating toxicity and hate speech:

RealToxicityPrompts²⁰. A dataset containing 100,000 naturally occurring prompts paired with toxicity scores. It assesses how language models generate toxic or non-toxic continuations from neutral or provocative inputs [110].

Toxigen²¹. A large-scale dataset of 274,000 toxic and benign statements targeting thirteen minority groups. It is used for adversarial and implicit hate speech detection [125].

Multilingual Multi-aspect Hate Speech Dataset²². A multilingual dataset (English, French, and Arabic) designed to evaluate hate speech and toxicity, featuring tweets annotated for emotions, toxicity, and targeted group associations [126].

Hurtlex²³. A lexicon containing offensive and hateful terms in over 50 languages, classified into 17 categories, with an additional macro-category for stereotypes [127].

Toxic Comment Classification Challenge²⁴. A dataset of 160,000 Wikipedia comments labelled by human annotators for toxicity, threats and other harmful content. It serves as a benchmark for toxic comment detection tasks [35].

Bias in dialogue systems and model behaviour encompasses issues like politeness, fairness, and alignment in conversational interactions. It is essential to evaluate and mitigate such biases to im-

¹⁵https://huggingface.co/datasets/crows_pairs

¹⁶<https://github.com/MilaNLPProc/honest>

¹⁷https://github.com/uclanlp/gn_glove

¹⁸<https://huggingface.co/datasets/McGill-NLP/stereoset>

¹⁹<https://huggingface.co/datasets/winogrande>

²⁰https://github.com/facebookresearch/ResponsibleNLP/tree/main/holistic_bias

²¹<https://github.com/microsoft/ToxiGen>

²²https://github.com/HKUST-KnowComp/MLMA_hate_speech

²³<https://github.com/valeribasile/hurtlex>

²⁴<https://www.kaggle.com/c/jigsaw-toxic-comment-classification-challenge/data>

prove user trust and satisfaction. A variety of datasets can be utilised to evaluate dialogue systems and model behaviour:

Big-bench²⁵. This directory contains tasks that are part of the Beyond the Imitation Game benchmark (BIG-bench). Each subdirectory contains a single benchmark task. There are 214 tasks in total including bias tests [128].

DialogueFairness²⁶. A dataset aimed at evaluating fairness in dialogue systems, focusing on attributes such as sentiment, politeness, diversity, and fairness across gender and racial groups [88].

Model-written Evaluation Datasets²⁷. A collection of 154 evaluation tasks generated by models to assess biases like sycophancy and persona alignment. It also includes modifications of Winogender datasets for dialogue agents [34].

Regard. A dataset with structured templates designed to measure language models' attitudes toward different demographic groups, focusing on regard-related attributes like respect and esteem [59].

TruthfulQA²⁸. A benchmark for testing the truthfulness of language models' responses. It includes 817 questions spanning 38 categories, evaluating biases in fact-based reasoning [129].

6.2 Tools

Several tools and frameworks have been developed for detecting biases and abusive languages in text, particularly in machine learning models, including LLMs. These tools range from evaluation frameworks to open-source toolkits and specialised metrics.

Hugging face provides an evaluation framework²⁹ for analysing the fairness and safety of LLMs. It includes metrics like Regard to measure the sentiment or respect expressed the model toward various demographic groups, helping evaluate bias related to regard in language generation; and Toxicity to assess the likelihood of generated text being toxic or harmful, enabling comprehensive evaluations of model behaviour.

PerspectiveAPI³⁰. PerspectiveAPI is a tool developed by Google Jigsaw for detecting toxicity in text. It provides a toxicity probability score for input text, making it one of the most widely used tools in the literature for analysing harmful or abusive language.

AI Fairness 360 (AIF360)³¹. AIF360 provides a comprehensive set of tools for measuring, diagnosing, and mitigating biases in machine learning models. It is particularly valuable for LLMs, offering algorithms and techniques to assess and improve fairness in AI systems.

Aequitas³². Aequitas focuses on auditing bias and fairness in machine learning tools. It assists data scientists and policymakers in identifying and mitigating systematic biases in predictions, including those from LLMs.

What-If Tool (WIT)³³. WIT is a code-free visualisation tool that enables users to probe machine learn-

²⁵<https://github.com/google/BIG-bench>

²⁶<https://github.com/zgahhblhc/DialogueFairness/blob/main/README.md>

²⁷<https://github.com/anthropics/evals>

²⁸<https://github.com/sylinrl/TruthfulQA>

²⁹<https://huggingface.co/docs/evaluate/en/index>

³⁰<https://perspectiveapi.com>

³¹<https://aif360.res.ibm.com>

³²<http://aequitas.dssg.io>

³³<https://pair-code.github.io/what-if-tool/>

ing models by exploring how predictions change based on different inputs. By identifying disparities in predictions across demographic groups, WIT is effective in uncovering biases in models.

Fairness Indicators³⁴. This tool integrates with WIT to assess bias in training data and model predictions. Fairness Indicators provide metrics such as disparity ratio and equal opportunity difference, which are critical for ensuring equitable model and performance across demographic groups.

SycophancyEval³⁵. The SycophancyEval framework extends existing evaluations of sycophancy by employing proof-of-concept multiple-choice questions where users explicitly state their preferences. This approach evaluates how language models align with or reinforce user-stated views [34, 65].

ROBBIE³⁶. ROBBIE framework focuses on benchmarking prompt-based bias and toxicity metrics. It compares six different metrics across 12 demographic axes and evaluates various bias and toxicity mitigation methods for multiple LLMs [121].

A variety of Python libraries provide tools for detecting and mitigating bias such as **bias-detector**³⁷, **Dbias**³⁸ to detect gender and race biases, and **Fairlearn**³⁹ for mitigating unfairness.

7 Discussion and Limitations

Bias detection serves as the foundation for identifying systematic disparities, while mitigation techniques aim to rectify or minimise these biases to ensure fairness and inclusivity. Evaluation methods, in turn, play a pivotal role in assessing the efficacy of these interventions, highlighting both their strengths and limitations. Together, these approaches form an interconnected framework that not only advances the technical landscape but also raises important ethical considerations. Although the works reviewed in this survey provide valuable insights into understanding bias in LLMs, illustrating numerous innovative approaches and techniques that represent significant advancements in the field, they are accompanied by notable limitations.

Metrics for measuring bias have evolved from static embeddings, such as Word2Vec [11] and Glove [12], to contextualised embeddings like BERT and GPT, which adapt dynamically to sentence context. Static embedding metrics, such as WEAT [14], measure association between target and attribute word sets but fail to account for context. SEAT [16] extends this to contextual embeddings but relies on predefined word sets, limiting its generalisability. Probabilistic metrics, such as DisCo [25] and LPBS [53], analyse token probabilities in templates to detect bias. DisCo uses dual-slot templates, while LPBS improves on it by addressing prior probability inconsistencies. Similarly, CrowS-Pairs Score [57] uses counterfactual pairs and pseudo-log-likelihood to identify stereotypical biases. However, these metrics depend on template design, making them sensitive to variations [64]. Approaches like Stereotype score [23] reveals stereotypes encoded in language models but face challenges with data instability and cross-lingual applicability [130]. Intrinsic biases can lead to stereotyping affecting downstream tasks [131]. Addressing contextual and linguistic sensitivity remains critical for robust bias detection. Intrinsic measures, such as DisCo, LPBS, SEAT, MAC, CrowS-Pairs, CAT and CEAT, are designed to evaluate biases within embeddings or model representations, aiming to quantify and eliminate specific variances. In contrast, extrinsic measures, like those used in

³⁴<https://research.google/blog/fairness-indicators-scalable-infrastructure-for-fair-ml-systems/?m=0>

³⁵<https://github.com/meg-tong/sycophancy-eval>

³⁶<https://github.com/facebookresearch/ResponsibleNLP/tree/main/robbie>

³⁷<https://pypi.org/project/biasdetector>

³⁸<https://pypi.org/project/Dbias/>

³⁹<https://pypi.org/project/fairlearn/0.4.2/>

downstream tasks such as occupation prediction or coreference resolution, evaluate how biases manifest in practical applications. Lastly, sycophancy metrics (e.g., [33]) evaluate a model’s tendency to align with user preferences often at the expense of factual accuracy. For instance, TruthfulQA [129] highlights this behaviour by assessing factuality in model responses. However, current sycophancy metrics are limited in scope, as they focus primarily on factual alignment while overlooking how user alignment may amplify biases or stereotypes.

Debiasing methods for LLMs are typically categorised into three phases: pre-processing, training, and post-processing. Each phase addresses biases at different levels of the model pipeline.

Pre-processing approaches mitigate biases by adjusting the data used to train the models. Techniques like counterfactual data augmentation and data balancing are used to ensure equal representation across social groups. For instance, gender-swapping [72] replaces gendered terms such as "he" with "she" to create balanced datasets. However, these methods can sometimes produce unnatural or contextually implausible sentences, which may limit their effectiveness. Similarly, data filtering [82], which involves removing discriminatory or harmful content from the training data, can reduce the generation of biased or toxic text but may also compromise the overall performance of the model. Projection-based mitigation [15] identifies and removes bias-laden subspaces in word embeddings, yet studies [132] show these methods often mask rather than remove biases entirely. Studies have showed that current approaches [15, 72], which depend on gender direction for the definition of gender bias and directly target it for the mitigation process, end up hiding the bias rather than reducing it [132]. Bias removal approaches based on gender direction are inefficient in removing all aspects of bias [15, 132]. In a high dimensional space, the spatial distribution of the gender-neutral word embeddings remains almost the same after debiasing. This enables a gender-neutral classifier to still pick up the cues that encode other semantic aspects of bias [58].

Training phase techniques modify the learning process to address biases. Loss function modification [58, 60, 86, 87] integrates fairness constraints into the optimisation process to reduce bias. Dropout regularisation and parameter updating refine model parameters to mitigate learned biases. Adversarial debiasing employs adversarial training to remove undesirable features, improving generalisation [61]. Additionally, human-in-the-loop methods incorporate human feedback during training to align models with ethical guidelines. While effective, these approaches are source-intensive as they often require retraining.

Post-processing approaches adjust model outputs without retraining the core system, making them ideal for closed-source models. While output rewriting [102, 103, 104, 105] focus on controlled text generation to enhance fairness, chain-of-thought prompting [112] guides model through step-by-step reasoning, improving fairness in outputs.

Emerging methods, like AXOLOTL [113], modify LLM behaviour by fine-tuning specific attributes. These approaches aim to align models with fairness principles without altering their foundational architecture. Lightweight and adaptive, they are promising for real-world deployment but require further refinement to address broader bias categories. DEXPERTS mitigates bias and toxicity in language model outputs by combining expert and anti-expert models to adjust token probabilities during decoding. It effectively steers text generation toward non-toxic outputs without requiring retraining, making it suitable for pre-trained or closed-source models. However, its reliance on the quality of expert and anti-expert models can limit effectiveness, and careful calibration is needed to avoid trade-offs, such as reduced diversity in text generation. Techniques like self-debiasing [108] modify token probabilities to suppress biased text generation. Esiobu et al. [121] observed that the self-debiasing technique is mostly effective in smaller LLMs, while prompting with hand-written templates and automatic prompt version for bias and toxicity detection are more effective in larger models. INLP [61] removes linearly encoded information from neural representations by projecting

it onto the null space of a classifier trained to predict protected attributes. However, it may not fully eliminate non-linear encodings, allowing non-linear models to still extract these attributes, limiting its ability to comprehensively mitigate bias. GBDD [107] is a technique to reduce both explicit and implicit biases in embedding spaces, but it has some limitations. One key challenge is the potential risk of inadvertently removing information that, while correlated with bias, is relevant and contextually important for specific tasks. For example, gendered information might be essential in specific applications (e.g., distinguishing king from queen). Lastly, Sent-Debias [29, 111] adjusts sentence embeddings by identifying a bias subspace and projecting the embeddings onto its orthogonal complement to remove bias-related components while preserving semantic meaning. While effective for linear biases, it may not address more complex, non-linear biases, limiting its scope in fully mitigating all forms of bias.

Datasets designed to measure bias are crucial for evaluating fairness in language models. These datasets often focus on biases related to gender, race, age, and socioeconomic status, helping identify and mitigate inequities. For example, template-based datasets use placeholders that language models fill with predefined demographic terms, exposing terms in the process. WinoBias [18] evaluates gender pronoun associations with occupations in stereotypical and counter-stereotypical contexts but limits gender to a binary framework. BUG [117] extends gender bias evaluation in machine translation using real-world English data, while GAP [39] offers a balanced corpus of ambiguous pronoun-name pairs for nuanced gender bias assessment. Datasets like CrowS-Pairs [57] evaluate stereotypes and pseudo-log-likelihood metrics. WinoQueer [27] measures anti LGBTQ+ stereotypes using over 45,000 sentences and diverse templates. Other notable datasets, such as BBQ [120], StereoSet [23], and BiasInBios [7], address biases related to professions, race, and gender. However, limitations exist; for instance, CrowS-Pairs has been criticised for its limited linguistic variety compared to datasets like Stereoset [97]. Generation-based datasets evaluate bias by prompting models to complete sentences based on prefixes. RealToxicityPrompts [110], one of the largest in this category, measures toxicity in generated text using curated prefixes and toxicity scores. BOLD [122] examines biases across professions, gender, race, religion, and politics. Other datasets, such as Multilingual Multi-Aspect Hate Speech [126] and Toxigen [125], focus on toxicity evaluation, including non-English contexts. Unintended bias in datasets with identity terms is often evaluated using synthetic data to group comments by identity and compare model performance.

Bias evaluation in dialogue systems is supported by datasets such as DialogueFairness [88], which tests for gender and racial biases, and TruthfulQA [129], which assesses models' tendencies to replicate human falsehoods. CALM [118] evaluates gender and racial bias across tasks like question answering and sentiment analysis using diverse templates. These datasets highlight biases in interactive contexts, which often differ from static evaluation settings. Finally, repositories like Big-Bench [128] aggregate benchmarks for evaluating stereotypes, gender biases, and demographic fairness. While these datasets provide valuable insights, many are limited in scope and fail to capture the full complexity of linguistic and contextual biases.

8 Open Problems and Future Directions

Bias in language models remains a significant issue, undermining fairness and trust in AI systems. While progress has been made in bias analysis, there are persistent limitations that require attention, as well as promising avenues for progress.

Inadequate Scope. Current research often focuses narrowly on specific types of biases, such as gender bias, while neglecting broader societal and demographic contexts [21]. For example, datasets

like WinoBias and Winogender schemas primarily address binary gender frameworks, leaving intersectional and nuanced biases under explored. Expanding the scope of research to include diverse categories, such as those represented in HolisticBias [22] and WinoQueer [27], can provide a more comprehensive understanding of biases across cultures and demographics. Future work should also emphasise analysing biases that manifest in underrepresented populations or intersectional contexts, which are often overlooked in existing studies.

Assumption About Bias. Many studies operate under the assumption that biases in training corpora are well-defined and observable. Biases are often subtle, latent, and context-dependent, making them difficult to detect. For instance, as Ouyang et al. [95] highlight, biases in systems like resume filtering tools may stem from omitted demographic information. Current datasets often strip context, such as the origin of the text or the demographic information of the author, which could provide critical insights for addressing bias detection and mitigation efforts by offering more granular information.

Data Quality. Training data often lacks diversity and fails to represent marginalised populations adequately. This disproportionately impacts minorities, as seen in the overestimation of toxicity for phrases like *I'm a gay man* or in dialects like African American English [42]. Counterfactual data augmentation techniques, while promising, often produce unnatural or contextually invalid sentences, reducing their utility in addressing biases. Future research should prioritise rational data replacement strategies and develop augmentation methods that generate natural, representative, and contextually valid data.

Algorithmic Complexity. Debiasing methods frequently rely on resource-intensive algorithms, which pose scalability challenges. Techniques like parameter-efficient-fine-tuning (e.g., PEFTDebias) are effective but lack generalisability beyond specific models such as BERT. Similarly, decoding modifications like DEXPERTS require expert models, which add computational overhead. Simplifying these methods while maintaining their effectiveness is crucial for large-scale application. Moreover, debiasing methods must go beyond superficial fixes, as masking biases often leaves underlying issues unresolved [132]. Scalable, generalisable, and interpretable approaches are essential to ensure robust bias mitigation.

Evaluation Metrics. The lack of standardised evaluation metrics complicates the assessment and comparison of bias mitigation methods. Metrics like WEAT and SEAT identify the presence of bias but fail to capture its impact on downstream tasks, such as coreference resolution or occupation prediction [111]. Even when embedding biases are minimised, issues like gender stereotypes can resurface in coreference resolution. There is a pressing need for metrics that evaluate biases across diverse tasks, sentence structures, and modalities, including user-agent interactions where biases may manifest as sycophancy or unfair treatment.

Addressing these challenges requires a combination of technical, societal, and policy-driven approaches. Improving data quality through adversarial sampling, domain-specific inclusivity, and advanced augmentation techniques will help create more representative datasets. Ensuring diversity in training data through inclusive collection practices and rigorous auditing is foundational to building robust and equitable systems. Moreover, research into scalable debiasing methods (e.g., [133, 134, 135]), such as fine-tuning with fairness-enhanced objectives, reweighting data contributions and using adversarial debiasing layers during training, offers promising avenues for practical bias mitigation. Furthermore, developing holistic frameworks for bias analysis and establishing standardised metrics for evaluation will enable a more consistent and comprehensive bias assessment.

Regular monitoring and updates, informed by real-world feedback and societal changes, should also be integrated into the lifecycle of these models. Progress requires a multidisciplinary approach that includes data diversification, scalable debiasing methods, standardised evaluation and collab-

orative policymaking. Ongoing research and regulatory measures are critical to ensuring that LLMs empower users equitably and minimise harm in diverse applications.

9 Conclusion

Language models offer incredible potential and utility, transforming industries and everyday tasks; however, it is essential to remain mindful of their limitations, particularly regarding bias, as they can reinforce harmful stereotypes and lead to unfair practices, making this a critical area of concern. This work presents a comprehensive survey of the literature on the types and sources of biases in LLMs, as well as their associated harms. It includes an extensive categorisation of bias detection methods, debiasing techniques, and evaluation resources, followed by an in-depth discussion of these approaches. Additionally, this study highlights promising directions for future bias research. By understanding what bias in language models look like and why it matters, we can take proactive steps to mitigate its impact, uncover hidden inequalities, and address them, striving to make AI systems as unbiased, equitable, and ethical as possible. This ensures that AI remains a tool for good, promoting fairness, inclusivity, and balanced perspectives.

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